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Relational Capital and Profitability: A Study of Consumer Goods Companies Listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc.

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Abstract

Following attention on pervasive corporate failures in Nigerian businesses and reporting structure, relational capital and its influence on profitability is a modern global corporate reporting issue. This research was carried out to examine the influence of relational capital on profitability of companies in the consumer goods sector in Nigeria. With a population of 21 companies in the consumer goods companies, a sample size of 17 companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc as at 31st December, 2024 were selected using purposive sampling techniques. To achieve the objectives, an ex-post facto research design was adopted involving manual generation of data from the annual reports of the selected companies. The study period was from 2015 to 2024 financial year. The actual values of relational capital were generated for each of the objectives in line with International Initiative on Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC). Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics specifically through simple regression techniques. Profitability of companies in the consumer goods companies was proxy by return on assets. Results revealed that, relational capital have a significant positive but weak influence on return on assets. This result was evidenced by a beta coefficient of 0.342 and probability value of 0.000. It was concluded that, with adequate relational capital in place in the company, firm's profitability and value creation would be achieved in the long term. It was recommended that, since relational capital is based on worldwide best practices and is intended to be reported to resource

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providers, particularly stakeholders, it should be considered a significant area of interest in the compilation of annual reports for businesses.

Keywords: Relational Capital, Profitability, Return on Assets and Consumer Goods Companies.

Introduction

Corporate information disclosures alone cannot guarantee corporate sustainability nor accurately reflect a firm's true financial position and profitability. Lopsided reporting may hinder firms from balancing corporate actions and activities with profitability and a sustainable outlook, especially in light of the recent paradigm shift in reporting priorities from stakeholder returns or traditional accounting to sustainability reporting, a framework that encompasses comprehensive disclosures. Profitability indicates how efficiently a business uses its resources to generate income for long-term viability. Organisations that utilise their resources effectively often generate more revenue for expansion.

Stakeholders are concerned about ensuring the company's sustainability in the near future, especially when corporate resources are underutilised, thereby jeopardising the organisation's survival and long-term prospects. It has long been observed that corporate reporting is often biased. The degree of partiality and distortion in the information disclosed may compromise stable business profitability and sustainability. This challenge is compounded by the ongoing shift from traditional financial reporting to sustainability reporting. Without an inclusive and balanced reporting framework, achieving a sustainable and profitable corporate position may be difficult.

According to a 2014 study by Turker and Sayer, financial reporting focuses on a limited aspect of a company's position and fails to convey to stakeholders the impact of social, environmental, and other sustainability-related issues. The concerns of enterprises often relate to their inability to enhance corporate image, evaluate profitability in accordance with societal expectations and regulations, or provide quantifiable data on environmental risks and opportunities. To address these limitations, the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) was established in 2013 by the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) as a new approach to corporate reporting. This framework ensures that organisations disclose all types of capital

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including financial, manufactured, intellectual, human, social or relational, and natural capital accurately. These capitals contribute to increasing or decreasing a company's value over time.

For effective reporting across industries, the IIRF should ideally be mandated in many countries. Therefore, companies, especially those seeking cross-border listings, should incorporate both the IIRF and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) frameworks into their annual reports and financial statements. For example, two companies that experienced significant financial success in previous decades, Oceanic Bank Plc. and Cadbury Plc., eventually faced the risk of collapse. Similarly, in 2001 and 2002, multinational corporations such as Enron and WorldCom experienced dramatic declines in profitability, making them vulnerable to corporate failure. These failures may have been due in part to a lack of an integrated reporting rationale. In support of this argument, Lajorin (2019) observed that approximately 20 percent of business transactions in Nigeria are recorded using a quantitative approach, while the remaining 80 percent rely primarily on fragmented reporting styles in annual reports.

Relational capital, a component of integrated reporting, provides a comprehensive assessment of a business's operations and activities. It utilises both financial and non-financial metrics within its reporting system. The current financial reporting system considers all capital sources including manufactured, financial, human or intellectual, social or relational, and natural capital. This represents a shift from traditional accounting fundamentals. The conventional system has faced widespread criticism for its shortcomings. In contrast, modern accounting systems offer clearer and more reliable reporting methods by including all forms of capital in company reports. This comprehensive approach facilitates informed decision-making and addresses the deficiencies of historically biased reporting systems.

Beyond its value-adding objective, relational capital, as part of integrated capital, significantly influences profitability. Several countries that participated in the IIRC pilot programme have adopted integrated reporting principles and adjusted their perspectives accordingly.

The global financial crisis of the 1990s in the United States led to the development of the IIRF, which was formally implemented in 2007 and remained in effect until 2009. The IIRF was introduced in response to the growing investor presence in capital markets and the need for sustained financial stability. It continues to serve diverse interests in advancing corporate reporting across various contexts.

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While neither the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) nor the Nigerian Business Statute mandates relational capital, it is gaining recognition in several African countries, notably Nigeria. This growing prominence is largely due to the establishment of the African Integrated Reporting Committee in alignment with the regulations of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN). Relational capital is seen as a critical component of a comprehensive wealth-building strategy. Consequently, integrated capital incorporates a wide range of financial and non-financial information to demonstrate how value is created now and in the future.

Although studies in developed countries suggest that information technology enhances corporate value, this assumption can only be validated in developing nations through the broad implementation of integrated capital. However, the subjective nature of integrated capital may complicate the evaluation of its benefits. This prompted the researcher to emphasise that, despite controversy, valuation remains essential in addressing societal needs.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate stakeholders' perspectives on relational capital and its impact on the profitability of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, while studies have examined relational capital in the context of integrated reporting and performance in Nigeria, none has empirically explored its relationship with profitability, measured by return on assets, within the country's consumer goods sector. The primary objective is to determine the distinct impact of relational capital on profitability in this industry.

2. Statement of the Problem

Profitability represents a vital component of any successful business. It is possible that improved profitability from the reporting approach in later years, as a result of relational capital in the first year, will lead to success in terms of profit and shareholder wealth maximisation. Profitability can therefore be determined in the annual reports of companies if all funds utilised in the business are carefully considered in the financial reports.

However, the lack of transparency around the reporting of profitability in most companies stems from the absence of relational capital, a component of sustainable capitals, in the annual reports of corporate entities. It would have been simpler and easier to evaluate profitability if the companies' annual reports had taken into account all types

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of capital at the same time. Hence, financial performance does not appear to be correlated with the quantity of capital utilised by a company to create value. This may be due to the historical dominance of financial and manufactured capitals in economic theories and business thinking. This raises the question of whether companies are exclusively employing these two types of capital to build value over time. Such a strategy might come at the expense of integrated capital, especially since stakeholders are increasingly concerned about the continued reporting of only manufactured and financial capitals, and the separate disclosure of sustainable capitals such as relational capital in annual reports.

A further question arises as to whether the financial and manufactured capital reporting approach remains the only effective means to improve a company's ability to continue operating and becoming profitable in the long term. Relational capital, as part of the components of integrated capital, is seen to have a greater influence on value creation and is regarded as a more effective means of enhancing a company's profitability. It is also considered an essential aspect of a comprehensive reporting system.

Research from the United States, the Netherlands, Japan, and South Africa, including studies by Adegbayegun et al. (2020) and Ebimobowei and Uche (2021), has demonstrated that a company's capacity to create value is essential to its ability to remain profitable. Studies have explored this subject to varying degrees of success, focusing on corporate finances and company value. Some studies have examined aspects of relational capital in relation to the cost of capital using generalised least squares as a research tool, while others have investigated structural capital and its influence on business profitability through longitudinal and mixed methods, incorporating firm characteristics.

Despite the range of analytical methods, demographic factors, and theoretical frameworks applied, the research conclusions remain inconclusive. Moreover, there is limited empirical research specifically addressing relational capital and its impact on the profitability of Nigerian consumer goods companies. It has not been clearly stated in the public domain whether relational capital, as a part of integrated capital, has influenced the profitability of this sector within the Nigerian economy. This study therefore examines the influence of relational capital on the profitability of Nigerian consumer goods companies, as measured by return on assets. The basic proposition of the study is

that relational capital does not significantly influence the profitability of these companies.

3. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

The interaction between relational capital and profitability within the context of consumer goods companies can be reasonably explained through stakeholder theory. The foundational concept of stakeholder theory was initially proposed by Mary Parker Follett nearly 60 years ago (Schilling, 2000) and was revived in the 1980s. According to Freeman (1984), a stakeholder is any group or individual that can affect or is affected by the achievement of an organisation's goals. Thus, stakeholders include both those who directly and indirectly have a vested interest in the company (Schilling, 2000).

Direct stakeholders typically include shareholders, employees, investors, customers, and suppliers, all of whom are closely tied to the company's profitability. Indirect stakeholders, such as the government and society, are also affected by corporate operations. Stakeholders such as owners, managers, employees, suppliers, creditors, debtors, government institutions, and the general public influence or are influenced by organisational objectives (Adegbayegun et al., 2020).

According to Gray et al. (1996), stakeholder theory acknowledges the complex and dynamic relationships between organisations and their stakeholders—relationships that encompass both responsibility and accountability. The theory integrates ethical and managerial dimensions. The ethical aspect insists on fair treatment of all stakeholders, while the managerial aspect focuses on satisfying the demands of powerful stakeholders whose support is critical for the organisation's survival. To meet the diverse informational needs of stakeholders, an integrated report must be developed (Adegbayegun et al., 2020).

Camilleri (2018) emphasises that relational capital reporting should be detailed enough to address stakeholders' specific informational requirements. Influential stakeholders can shape managerial decisions in ways that support not only financial outcomes but also social and environmental goals. Clarke (2004) similarly viewed organisations as multilateral agreements between a business and its stakeholders, governed by both formal and informal rules developed through ongoing interactions.

Although shareholders may provide financial capital, managers depend on employees and other stakeholders to drive the company's productivity and performance.

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Over time, the narrow focus on shareholders has broadened to include the concerns of other stakeholders, such as those related to social responsibility, environmental impact, and ethical governance (Freeman, 1984; Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Freeman et al. (2004) argue that focusing on shareholder value can lead to improved outcomes for all stakeholders, though they also acknowledge the challenges managers face in identifying and balancing a wide array of stakeholder interests.

Stakeholder theory aligns well with the objective of this study, as it helps explain the factors that sustain organisational continuity and underscores the importance of incorporating diverse stakeholder interests into decision-making, especially when integrated reporting is applied. It provides a theoretical foundation for examining how firms' financial characteristics influence the reporting of relational capital in Nigeria's consumer goods sector. For value maximisation to be realised and stakeholder interests to be served through stable profitability, this study supports the stakeholder theory.

Corporate reporting is an ever-evolving field as companies strive to improve communication with stakeholders. One of the most important means of achieving this is through the annual reporting of relational capital. Relational capital aligns relevant information about an organisation's strategy, governance, performance, and future prospects, reflecting its economic, environmental, and social impact within its operating environment. Its primary aim is to explain how value is created over time through relationships and stakeholder engagement.

Relational capital is increasingly recognised as a critical aspect of a firm's influence on society and the economy. According to the IIRC (2013), integrated capital includes financial, manufactured, human/intellectual, social and relationship, and natural capitals. However, this study focuses on relational capital.

Relational capital comprises the institutions and relationships within and between communities, stakeholder groups, and networks, along with the capacity to share information to promote individual and collective well-being. It includes shared norms, common values, behaviour, stakeholder relationships, and the trust an organisation develops and maintains with external parties. These intangibles—such as brand reputation and social licence to operate—form the foundation of relational capital. Unlike financial capital, it stems from interpersonal relationships that foster action and cooperation. Social interactions thus become a vital resource (Coleman, 1988). Putnam (2004) identified trust as a central component, defining relational capital

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as a network of norms and social trust that promotes collaboration for mutual benefit. Although definitions vary, Keeley (2005) argued that relational capital requires present sacrifices for future benefits—for example, prioritising community engagement over short-term gains. According to the IIRC (2013), relational capital is a necessary precondition for sustainable value creation. It includes the shared traditions, norms, and trust cultivated within and outside the organisation, as well as the stakeholders' willingness to engage. Putnam (2004) considered the ability of individuals and organisations to work together toward common goals, especially between corporations and external stakeholders such as communities and shareholders, as a key social network feature of relational capital.

Relational capital encompasses the quality of supply chain relationships, community acceptance, governmental ties, and competitor interactions. Building these relationships is essential for maintaining a company's social licence to operate. Education also enhances social capital and complements other capitals, such as human/intellectual capital, forming a virtuous cycle (Putnam, 2004; Ajekwe, 2019).

Riahi-Belkaoui (2004) included within relational capital the systematic selection of social performance indicators and the generation of meaningful data to assess corporate social impact. Similarly, Andrew and Tsang (2015) defined it as the collective resources accessed and generated through an organisation's network of trusted relationships. Relational capital therefore encompasses how stakeholders, including customers and communities, interact with the organisation. It plays a role in identifying opportunities for partnerships, joint ventures, and business growth, including the ability to attract investment and negotiate effectively (Lajorin, 2019).

The institutions and linkages across communities and stakeholder groups that enable effective information exchange are key features of relational capital. These include shared values, behaviours, and social norms. According to Adegbe et al. (2019) and Nwankwo et al. (2020), relational capital can attribute monetary value to social relationships, institutions, and norms. It is arguably as valuable as financial capital, arising from human interactions that generate ideas, knowledge, and future opportunities. The strength of internal and external networks can influence organisational performance and trust, leading to economic success (Adegbe et al., 2019; Nwankwo et al., 2020).

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In this study, relational capital is measured by the value of investments in philanthropy, particularly donations. To assess profitability, this study employs the return on assets (ROA) indicator, which captures how efficiently a company utilises its total assets to generate profit. ROA reflects the earnings produced relative to asset investment (Suresh, 2018). Ewereoke (2018) computed ROA by dividing income before interest and taxes by total assets, excluding tax effects since they are largely outside managerial control. A higher ROA signifies better financial performance. ROA provides a reliable comparison between similar businesses and was adopted in this study to evaluate the overall financial health of Nigerian consumer goods companies.

Nuraini et al. (2023) examined how community empowerment and social capital affect agricultural production capacity in Indonesia. The study used a deductive method and survey design to propose and evaluate a research model involving three latent variables: community empowerment, social capital, and production capacity. Five indicators—possibility, strengthening, protection, support, and maintenance—were used to measure community empowerment, while three indicators—social linking, social bridging, and social bonding—measured social capital. Four metrics assessed production capacity: infrastructure, agriculture, commodity, and marketing.

Data were collected through multistage sampling from 500 farmers, with 100 valid responses obtained. A structured questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale and was analysed using Smart PLS 3.0. Descriptive statistics described respondent characteristics, while structural equation modelling (SEM) was used for inferential analysis. The model employed path analysis and assessed outer and inner models for indicator relationships and latent variables.

Findings showed that community empowerment had a positive effect on social capital, which in turn enhanced production capacity. Social capital fully mediated the relationship between community empowerment and production. These results provide useful insights for researchers and practitioners on improving production development through enhanced stakeholder engagement and community relationships.

Alfiyanto and Sukarno (2023) analysed the influence of employee engagement and relational capital on employee performance at PT Eka Tama Makmur Surabaya. Key aspects of human resource management included the organisation, administration, and implementation of staffing programmes to enhance productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness. The study aimed to determine how relational capital and employee

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engagement affect employee performance at PT Eka Tama Makmur Surabaya. The research employed survey and ex-post facto designs. All marketing employees of the company, totalling 40 by 2021, constituted the study population. Saturated sampling, a form of non-probability sampling, was adopted. Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis was conducted using SmartPLS software. Results revealed a positive correlation between employee engagement and performance, indicating that greater involvement leads to improved outcomes. Relational capital also showed a positive association with performance, suggesting that a robust relational capital framework enhances employee effectiveness.

Erickson and Rothberg (2023) investigated relational capital in the context of media brands, extending a prior study focused on developing new metrics for relational capital. Relational capital, a significant component of intellectual capital, pertains to external relationships, unlike human capital, which relates to job-specific knowledge, or structural capital, which is embedded in organisational systems. It concerns managing external interactions, particularly with customers. Despite its relevance to brand equity, relational capital remains underexplored in knowledge management research. Brand equity, rooted in a firm's history of customer interactions, is intrinsically linked to relational capital. Understanding customer satisfaction is key to building brand equity, although standardised methods for measuring it are lacking. High-value brands are often assessed through consultancy rankings. The study used Salesforce Social Studio, a web-scraping tool, to conduct brand sentiment analysis. Data on brand mentions, sentiment, sources, influencers, and languages were collected over three months in early 2023. The analysis covered established media outlets like the *New York Times* and *Wall Street Journal*, as well as emerging brands like BuzzFeed and TechCrunch. The study combined sentiment analysis with a survey design. Results showed that while some trends were evident, others were not, as fluctuations in engagement were often driven by current events. The findings provided insight into which metrics should be tracked to assess the evolving value of relational capital.

Zhang (2022) explored the relationship between social capital, income, and subjective well-being in rural China. The study considered how social and relational capital impact individual well-being in a society like China. Using data from the China Household Income Survey (CHIPs) collected in 2003, the study examined 9,200 rural households across 12 provinces. An ordered logistic regression model was applied to

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analyse how income, social engagement, and reciprocity relate to well-being. The findings demonstrated that income and social capital significantly contribute to subjective well-being. The study proposed policy recommendations based on these results, focusing on improving social engagement and reciprocal support.

Bekanwah et al. (2020) examined the relationship between relational capital and business growth in Nigerian manufacturing firms. The study adopted a cross-sectional design, enabling data collection from businesses across various locations. The target population comprised all manufacturing companies in Rivers State, focusing on six firms and 160 managers and supervisors. Data were gathered using questionnaires, and analysis was conducted using Pearson's correlation. The results showed a strong relationship between relational capital and business growth. The researchers recommended that firms cultivate strong ties with suppliers, customers, and the public to foster sustainable expansion.

Nguyen et al. (2019) investigated the impact of relational capital on supply chain collaboration and its effects on both radical and incremental innovation in China. The study proposed a theoretical model linking relational capital to three collaborative dimensions and innovation types. A quantitative methodology was employed, surveying 225 suppliers in Hunan between 2015 and 2016. Analytical techniques included exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, along with structural equation modelling. Findings indicated that relational capital significantly supports knowledge sharing and mutual benefit, which in turn promotes innovation. The study concluded that businesses should leverage relational capital to foster sustainable partnerships and achieve innovation, offering recommendations for strategy development in collaborative environments.

Ocicka and Wieteska (2019) explored how to measure relational capital in supply chains. Their literature review, spanning studies from 2004 to 2018, involved keyword searches, screening, and article analysis to identify variables and metrics for assessing buyer-supplier relational capital. The review revealed that interactions between buyers and sellers can enhance competitive advantage and organisational value. However, relational capital as a component of social capital remains under-researched in supply chain contexts. The authors proposed a five-element construct comprising commitment, interaction, respect, reciprocity, and trust. Despite some limitations, the study contributed to the development of a framework for measuring relational capital in supply chain relationships.

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5. Methodology

An ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study, allowing the use of historical data on relational capital and profitability to determine their influence. The study population comprised all 21 consumer goods companies in the sector. A sample of 17 companies was selected using Taro Yamane's formula, with purposive sampling employed to choose the sample units. Secondary data were utilised, sourced from the annual reports of the selected companies covering the period from 2015 to 2024. In testing the isolated influence of relational capital on profitability of the sector, a simple econometric model was utilised and the formula was stated as follows;

$$Y=f(x) \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

Where:

Y is the profitability measured by return on assets. X is the relational capital (RC). In a functional form, it was stated as;

$$ROA = f(RC) \quad \text{Hypothesis one}$$

Substituting profitability and relational capital variables in a regression statistics equation, the following model was developed thus;

$$ROA_{it} = \Omega_0 + \Omega_1(RC)_{it} + e_{it} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where: ROA	=	Return on Assets
Ω_0	=	Constant Terms
Ω_1	=	Estimated Coefficients of the independent variables
RC	=	Relational Capital
e	=	Error term
i	=	Number of Companies
t	=	Number of years

For analytical details, this is stated in the hypothesis below:

H₀: There is no significant influence of relational capital on return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

6. Data Analyses and Findings

The hypothesis was tested through simple regression analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.0 at 5% level of significance. However, the results were stated as follows.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics
Profitability (ROA) (%)	170	-235.99	617.43	7.5224	57.84140	7.447	80.110
Relational Capital(N'000)	170	0.00	47,545,560.00	647,777.4000	3,868,674.47684	10.845	129.676
Valid N (listwise)	170						

Source: *Researcher's Computation (2025)*

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. Profitability, proxied by return on assets (ROA), served as the dependent variable. The ROA ranged from a minimum of -235.99% to a maximum of 617.43%, with a mean of 7.52% and a standard deviation of 57.84%. This indicates substantial variability in profitability, with the mean and standard deviation differing by 50.32%. The coefficient of skewness (7.45) suggests that the distribution is positively skewed, indicating that the data are asymmetrical and tilted to the right. Furthermore, the kurtosis value of 80.11 indicates a leptokurtic distribution, meaning the data are highly peaked with a thin bell shape and heavy tails. These characteristics fall within acceptable statistical norms.

Relational capital was measured by the value of donations. As shown in Table 4.1, donations ranged from a minimum of ₦0.00 to a maximum of ₦47,545,560.00, with a mean of ₦647,777.40 and a standard deviation of ₦3,868,674.48. The high standard deviation reflects significant dispersion around the mean. The skewness coefficient of 10.85 indicates a strong positive skew, while the kurtosis value of 129.68 suggests a highly peaked (leptokurtic) distribution. This implies that the data are asymmetrical, concentrated around the mean, and meet the criteria for acceptable statistical properties.

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Test of Hypothesis

The research hypothesis was tested in this section of the study. The test was carried out using ordinary least square regression with the model specification showed below using Statistical Package for Social Science version 25.0 software. The result of the analysis is shown in the study below.

Ho₁: There is no significant influence between relational capital and return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Regression Summary on the influence of RC on ROA of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.342 ^a	.117	.109	.77971	1.522

a. Predictor: (Constant), Relational Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2025)

Table 4.3: ANOVA Summary on the influence of RC on ROA of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	8.530	1	8.530	14.031	.000 ^b
1	Residual	64.443	168	.608		
	Total	72.974	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Relational Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2025)

Table 4.4: Regression Coefficient on the influence of RC on ROA of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	5.259	.347		15.159	.000		
	Relational Capital	.272	.072	.342	3.746	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2025)

Table 4.2, presents the summary of the influence of relational capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The R-square of 0.117 indicated that 11.7% of the relational capital really contributed to the return on assets of the listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria and is explained in the regression model. Table 4.3 showed a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted. It can be inferred that there is a significant positive influence of relational capital on return on assets of the listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was confirmed by the t-calculated of 3.746 against the critical value of t which was represented by 1.962. Table 4.4 showed a beta coefficient of 0.342 for relational capital implying that, if other variables are held constant, as relational capital increases, return on assets increases respectively in that magnitude. Therefore, a N1 increase in relational capital would lead to a N0.342 increase in return on assets.

7. Discussion of the Findings

Motivated by the need to examine whether relational capital influences the profitability of consumer goods companies in Nigeria, one hypothesis was formulated and tested. Data spanning ten years across seventeen consumer goods companies were collected and analysed, and the results discussed.

The hypothesis yielded a t-statistic of 3.746 and a probability value of 0.000, which is below the 0.05 significance threshold. The regression coefficient was 0.342, indicating a statistically significant but weak positive influence of relational capital on return on assets. This suggests that relational capital exerts a modest positive impact on the profitability of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Specifically, a unit increase in relational capital is associated with an increase of approximately ₦34.20 in return on assets, implying that efficient utilisation of existing intangible resources can contribute to value creation.

This finding supports the argument that relational capital (through strengthened stakeholder relationships, trust, and engagement) plays a role in enhancing financial performance. It also aligns with the study by Nguyen et al. (2019), which reported a significant relationship between relational capital and supply chain collaboration for both radical and incremental innovation among 225 vendors in the Hunan region of China. The result reinforces the importance of relational capital in fostering value-added interactions and long-term corporate profitability.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

Drawing from the test results, the researchers conclude a significant positive but weak influence of relational capital on return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, relational capital exerts the most significant but weak influence on return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, the researchers recommended as follows:

- i. Since capitals act as a company's growth engine and benefit Nigerian stakeholders, regulatory authorities ought to mandate relational capital, a component of integrated capital, rather than letting listed firms choose not to participate in it.
- ii. Relational capital should be fully implemented by regulators on integrated capital and standard-setters for accounting. Consumer goods companies would benefit from this and would be helped to transition from the conventional reporting technique to the global best practices.
- iii. Nigerian listed businesses should keep an eye on non-compliance with relational capital reporting guidelines and penalize violators accordingly.
- iv. More investment should be put in place by the consumer goods companies, as it is

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the foundation for a thriving business and society and is focused on a company's profitability.

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